

THE THEORY OF READING COMPREHENSION

Mo'minova Mahliyo Ahrorjonovna

Namangan davlat universiteti 2-kurs doktoranti

e-mail: mahliyomominova76@gmail.com

tel raqami: +99894 -492-00-41

Annotation: *In this article considers the importance of developing a satisfactory theory of reading and comprehension. It reviews how various theories and models of reading and comprehension have developed over the past century or so, paying particular attention to those that stress the active and constructive nature of process.*

Key words: *Theory, reading, reader, comprehension, page, text, general context, information.*

Any adequate theory or definition of reading must account for the multiple levels of cognitive processing involved. At the lower levels lie the perceptual processes, beginning with the identification of handwritten or printed symbols on a page or on a computer screen. Beyond this initial decoding level are the processes by means of which the reader retrieves lexical entries from the lexicon and the parses a string of words to assemble a syntactic structure and add semantic content. Huey was one of several early reading researchers who recognized reading to be a conceptual as well as a perceptual process. A few years later, Thorndike (1917/1972) suggested that reading comprehension called upon the reader's reasoning as well as their perceptual powers. Even at this early stage in reading comprehension research, Thorndike recognized the importance of "the mental set" which could cover not only the contextual feature of purpose Fries (1945,1963) and Gray (1948) also recognized the reader's background knowledge as a potentially significant influence in the reading comprehension process, although empirical investigation of this and similar influences had to wait another two or three decades.

Jenkinson (1072) suggested that the earliest attempt to model the reading process was probably that of Gray (1960) who proposed four different activities: word perception, comprehension, reaction to what is read, and assimilation of what is read through the fusion of old and new ideas. Gray seems to have drawn a distinction between "comprehension", which related to the literal and implied meaning of the text, and assimilation, where readers relate what they have read to their background knowledge. Samuel and Kamil (1988) suggested that although theories concerning components of reading process had existed in the minds of some researchers for several years "There was simply not a strong tradition of attempting to conceptualize knowledge and theory about the reading process in the form of explicit reading models" [1988:22]. The 1920s and 1970s, however, witnessed the development of several different models describing the reading process, some more detailed than others, and some

lending themselves more readily to empirical investigation and validation than others. Vacca and Vacca (1983) referred to the 1970s as “an era of unrepresented advances in theory and model building leading to renaissance in research on the reading process” [1983:382].

Three different theories of how readers were believed to arrive at an understanding of text are described in more detail below- *bottom-up*, *top-down*, and *interactive* - along with specific examples of their proponents. Urquhart and Weir [1998:39-46] classified all three as “process models” due to their focus on processing, while Grabe and Stoller [2002:31] referred to them as “metaphorical models” representing generalizations that arose from comprehension research over the previous three decades.

So-called bottom-up processing models of reading regarded the flow of information from initial incoming data to final interpretation of meaning on the part of the reader as uni-directional, passing through a series of discrete stages. Each stage had the function of transforming incoming input and sending the recoded information up to the next stage for further transformation and recording. Cohen and Upton and Birch provide all full explanation of bottom-up models.

Proponents of so-called top-down processing models claimed that, instead of moving up from the bottom, readers generate an understanding of text by working in the opposite direction, using their ability to anticipate, hypothesise and confirm or disconfirm on basis of context. Goodman (1967) proposed the concept of the reader as a more active participant in the reading process than had recognized. Using insights and methodology drawn from the fields of psycholinguistics, he set about designing a model of the reading process which would be “powerful enough to explain and predict reading behavior and sound enough to be a base on which to build and examine the effectiveness or reading instruction” [1988:11].

Interactive processing models of reading is frequently used to describe the nature of the relationship which can exist between a text and a reader, or even between the various elements within a text. Grabe [1991:384] suggested that while top-down and bottom-up models were “seral” in nature, interactive models hypothesised a parallel processing approach in reading in which every level or component can interact with any other. Both Rumelhart (1977) and Stanovich (1980) produced examples of interactive processing models of reading.

Stanovich (1980) claimed that “Interactive models of reading appear to provide a more accurate conceptualization of reading performance than do strictly top-down or bottom-up models” [1980:32].

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